

PROSPECTS OF USING HISTORICAL-CULTURAL TOURISM IN NAVOYI REGION

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Abstract. The article discusses the socio-economic significance of historical and cultural tourism, its role in increasing the income of the country's population, the tourism potential of the Navoi region and the prospects for its use.

Keywords: Historical and cultural tourism , income , population income , tourist potential , cultural heritage , foreign exchange.

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Each country has its own geographical location, natural resources, opportunities for the development of economic sectors, as well as history, culture, customs, and traditions. Only those countries that have effectively used these opportunities for the development of their countries can claim to be superior in development. The unique geographical location of Uzbekistan, far from the seas and the lack of water transport links with developed economic centers of the world, to a certain extent limit the country's integration into the world economic system. Therefore, many researchers rightly consider tourism to be one of the most important resources for the development of Uzbekistan. Most importantly, Uzbekistan has great opportunities for the development of this sector of the economy due to its rich and in many ways unique historical and cultural heritage. In addition, Uzbekistan has unique beautiful nature, landscapes (deserts, steppes, mountains, lowlands), a variety of unique flora and fauna, as well as archaeological finds and paleontological remains of world importance, which can be used as a tourist resource. These historical elements (finds) are of great importance in attracting tourists.

Considering the abundance of historical and cultural monuments in Uzbekistan and the fact that their effective use can have a strong impact on economic growth, we believe that the development of historical and cultural tourism in the country will be more profitable than other types of tourism. The rapid development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan, including a careful attitude to historical and cultural heritage, the creation of infrastructure that fully meets international standards, and the strengthening of international ties, can turn our region into one of the most visited countries in the world and turn tourism into one of the main sources of income.

Historical and cultural tourism has great economic and, at the same time , important social significance. Its social content is to provide employment for the country's population, broaden tourists' worldviews about the environment and existence, and attract people from all over the world by showing the country's centuries-old past and rich culture. The economic significance of historical and cultural tourism is manifested in its ability to increase the income of the country's population, improve their standard of living, satisfy their material needs, and other aspects.

Therefore, it is of great theoretical and practical importance to first understand the scientific foundations of increasing the socio-economic content and effectiveness of cultural tourism, and to conduct a broad and comprehensive analysis.

Currently, the efficiency of using historical and cultural tourist sites in Navoi region is also increasing significantly from year to year. For example, in 2018, 27.1 thousand foreign tourists from 30 foreign countries visited the region, while in 2019, 57.4 thousand foreign tourists from 53 foreign countries visited it. Also, 9 thousand foreign tourists visited it in 2021. At the same time, the number of local tourists exceeded 2,404 thousand during the 12 months of 2019, an increase of 27% compared to 2018 (1,895 thousand people). In 2021, 522 thousand local tourists visited it. Also, in 2021, in accordance with the Domestic Tourism Development Program, 55 thousand employees of 77 enterprises and organizations in the region and 169 thousand citizens from 307 community civic gatherings were involved in domestic tourism, and a total of about 250 thousand people were organized for trips. Today, the total number of tourist accommodation facilities in the region has reached 158, with 2,012 rooms and 4,792 beds. Of these, 37 are hotels, 88 are family guest houses, 24 are hostels, 5 are recreation centers, and 4 are mountain camps. It should be noted that in 2016, the number of guest houses was 1, while by March 2023, it was increased to 88, creating 120 new jobs. Within the framework of the "Regional Investment Program for 2020-2021", 1 project was launched in 2021 by absorbing foreign investments worth \$ 300 thousand, thereby absorbing the investment, fulfilling the annual plan by 100%, and creating 15 new jobs. In particular, in order to further develop the tourism sector in Navoi region, a total of 7 projects worth a total of 12 billion soums were implemented in 2021. As a result, 7 new hotels (154 rooms, 235 beds) were launched, creating a total of 68 new jobs.

In order to further promote the region's tourism potential, about 70 promotional materials, including tourist maps, tourist booklets and brochures, were prepared and distributed to foreign guests at tourism information centers, hotels, tour operators, and republican-level exhibitions and forums, and various promotional activities were carried out through about 100 foreign media outlets and bloggers.

In our opinion, all tourist routes should be developed starting from Navoi region. Because the extensive operation of the Navoi FEEZ, which has begun, requires foreign and domestic citizens and visitors to start their tourist routes from Navoi city. This is a great opportunity for the development of tourism. It is only necessary to use it rationally. In turn, this will allow the implementation of the resolution of the Navoi region administration dated October 12, 2017 "Measures on the organization of "guest houses" for vacationers and tourists in private homes with modern conditions".

Navoi region is located in the northwest of the Kyzylkum desert, in the southeast of the Nurota mountain range, and in the middle reaches of the Zarafshan River, which allows the population to engage in agriculture. Not only the Zarafshan River, but also many large water bodies such as Aydarkul, Shurkul, and Tudakul contribute to the diversity of the region's nature. Although Navoi is a young and youthful region, it has an ancient and unique history that has made a great contribution to human civilization. In particular, the unique architectural monuments of Raboti Malik Caravanserai and Sardoba, Kasim Sheikh Azizon Khanaqah, and Nurota are invaluable cultural heritage.

It is no secret that archaeological research conducted in the Tashurmon and Sarmishsay gorges in the city of Uchkuduk, Navoi region, and in the villages of Uchtut, Ijand, and Sangbursay in the present-day Navbahor district, revealed tools of Stone Age hunters and primitive rock paintings, which were included in the UNESCO list of historical monuments.

In our opinion, in order to increase the effectiveness of the use of historical and cultural tourist objects in the Navoi region, it is appropriate to implement the following:

- implementation of reconstruction and restoration works in historical and cultural objects;

organize the writing of the names of the places on a large and visible background at the entrance to the territory of historical and cultural tourist sites;

- installing information boards in three languages (Uzbek, Russian, English) at the entrance to historical and cultural tourist sites, providing information about the history of the site, relevant facts, and necessary information about them, and posting them on social networks;

- Establishing Internet and Wi-Fi systems at every historical site and recreation area, and creating official websites for pilgrimage sites;

- it is necessary to organize separate toilets, prayer rooms and showers in the areas of the shrine, as well as to set their location and indicators.

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